

DETERMINING THE OPTIMAL PROCESSING VOLUME OF OIL THAT SATISFIES THE DEMAND FOR RAW MATERIALS OF THE PETROCHEMICAL INDUSTRY

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Abstract

The demand for oil refining and petrochemical products of our country has been analyzed in various aspects, these aspects are as follows.

- Consumption of petroleum products in our country;
- Worldwide per capita demand.

This article presents the analysis of the prospective demand for oil refining and petrochemical products of the domestic market from various aspects and the result of the research conducted in the direction of determining the minimum volume of oil processing in the country based on it.

Keywords: demand, gasoline, jet fuel, diesel fuel, motor fuel, hydrocarbon, oil, transport, kerosene.

Introduction

The industries that have the greatest beneficial impact on the world in various ways are oil and gas production, their processing and petrochemical sectors. The oil sector, which combines petrochemical gas and oil companies, is one of the largest sectors in which almost every activity operates. After extensive processing in oil refineries, crude oil is one of the main factors used in the preparation of all petrochemicals and petroleum components. Gasoline, diesel fuel, kerosene, lubricating oil, and liquefied petroleum gas are the main hydrocarbon products refined from petroleum. It is used as a raw material in the petrochemical industry, which produces oil and natural gas products. The final products produced in this process are called petrochemical products. The petrochemical industry uses raw materials such as ethylene, propylene, benzene, and toluene [1-4].

The establishment of environmental problems is subject to stringent requirements imposed on petroleum refining and petrochemical products and production. These requirements require the removal of sulfur in fuels and benzene in automatic compounds. Since ethane and methane obtained from natural gas are widely used as the main raw materials, major changes have taken place in the petrochemical sector. As these raw materials are more affordable, investments in gas-based petrochemical industries have increased in markets with natural gas such as the United States, the Middle East, and the Gulf region [5, 6].

The two main raw materials used to produce petrochemicals are natural gas and crude oil. As natural gas and crude oil are often intermediate products, it is possible to use various methods to obtain recycled products. The intermediates can be more heavy hydrocarbons such as naphtha or gasoil, or lighter hydrocarbon molecules such as ethane and methane. Diesel and naphtha are two derivatives of crude oil with different boiling points. Oil sands are complex carbonaceous raw minerals that can be used as oil shale and coal energy and power sources. However, they must go through lengthy and thorough processing procedures before

they can create fuels and products made from petroleum-based raw materials and mineral raw materials produced from coal and oil shale. Primary raw materials for the production of basic plastics are usable olefins obtained from cracking gases (gas-based petrochemical products) such as naphtha or butylene, propylene, ethylene. Naphtha cracking is used to produce olefins, which are more readily available and require less energy than gases [7-9].

Main Research Material

Demand is a dynamic indicator, it depends on the country's economy and technology development, population growth, etc. At the same time, the volume of demand is a quantity that always depends on the standard of living.

There are a number of methods for determining the demand for oil products. These methods are developed by multi-factor analysis method. Examples of these factors are transport supply, population demand for cars, living standard of the region, ratio of fuel production and consumption, etc. can be shown. The main factor here is the population size and annual growth. At the same time, the number of cars per 1,000 people and the distribution of cars by economic zones apply here. Based on statistical data, it can be noted that the total number of cars in Azerbaijan has increased by approximately 2.2 times in the last 10 years.

The increase in the number of cars increases the volume of fuel consumption. The analysis of statistical data in the last 10 years shows that the demand for gasoline has increased significantly. At present, the demand for motor fuels in our capital is even greater, as car parks are mainly located in Baku. The per capita demand for gasoline in Baku is 316 kg per year, in Sumgait - 11 kg, in Ganja - 27 kg, and in Nakhchivan - 74 kg. On average, the demand for gasoline in Azerbaijan is 148 kg.

Automotive gasoline makes up half of the refinery's output. Although the composition of all automotive fuels is basically the same, they have significant differences. Gasoline is produced in a variety of ways

by mixing refined hydrocarbon streams and adding additives. Basically, gasoline is obtained from a mixture of light substances collected in the upper layers of oil installations. They are mixed with 3 main quality differences in mind. Volatility or evaporability (the ability to help start an engine), clean burning and octane rating (an indicator of combustibility). Chemical additives are intended to prevent engine deposits, carburetor freezes, and other potential problems. It is also very important that the fuel is free from water and other foreign substances. It should be noted that gasoline is produced in AI-92, AI-95, AI-98 brands. Car gasolines are issued in 2 types: summer and winter gasolines. It should be noted that the winter time has good evaporation ability, which is useful for the machine to start quickly, while the summer time can cause steam congestion and rapid heating problems. This is one of the reasons why refineries adjust gasoline blends according to seasons and different geographical zones. Engine fuels are used not only to meet the needs of motor vehicles, but also for various purposes.

Taking into account the consumption of motor fuels in the country, the dynamics of automobiles, the type of fuel used in cars and the dynamics of consumption, the demand for these products in the republic was predicted. In the near future, the demand for gasoline will be 180-190 kg, and the demand for diesel fuel will be 180-200 kg. During those years (2012-2022), taking into account the population, the demand for engine fuels (jet fuel, diesel fuel and gasoline) of the republic is given as a forecast chart.

The volume of domestic demand for oil products does not reflect the demand, because the demand is limited by the purchasing power of the population, although the demand is large, the sales volume may decrease if the purchasing power is low. In order to determine the optimal volume of oil processing, first of all, the population's demand for oil processing and petrochemical products was analyzed in Table 1. When forecasting the demand for the main oil refining products in Azerbaijan, the population growth trend was taken into account in Figure 1.

Table 1.

The population's demand for oil processing and petrochemical products

Indicators	Per capita demand of the population	General demand
Automotive gasoline	160-360	1520-3420
Diesel fuel	180-400	1710-3800
Jet fuel	40-90	380-855
Polyethylene	20	190
Polypropylene	10	95

Figure 1. Forecast of demand for motor fuels in Azerbaijan

Conclusions

It has been determined that the processing of 6.0 mln.t/year of oil currently meets the country's demand. In the near future, the minimum amount of oil to meet the country's demand is set at 8.0 mln.t/year. The perspective is that due to the increase in the population and the development of the petrochemical industry, the minimum oil processing volume will be 10.0 mln.t/year.

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